

RESEARCH ARTICLE

**ETHNOBOTANICAL EXPLORATION AND
PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING OF *JUSTICIA ADHATODA* L:
A CASE STUDY FROM BARGARH DISTRICT, ODISHA, INDIA****Krishna Bhoi¹, Rahul Sahu¹, Nihar Ranjan Nayak²,
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Abstract:

The present study involved the ethnobotanical exploration and qualitative phytochemical analysis from the leaves of *Justicia adhatoda* L. plant. The native of Bargarh district used the leaves of *J. adhatoda* for the treatment of asthma, arthritis, colds, coughs, eczema, malaria, tuberculosis and rheumatism, and as a uterine tonic. The phytochemical screening revealed presence of phytochemicals like alkaloids, steroids, terpenoids, saponins, phenols and tannins in the ethanol extract, while flavonoids, cardiac glycosides, amino acids, proteins, carbohydrates and reducing sugar were found to be absent. Meanwhile, In the aqueous extracts, alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, saponins, tannins, phenols, amino acids and proteins showed positive result, but steroids, tannins, cardiac glycosides, carbohydrates and reducing sugars showed negative result.

Keyword: *Justicia adhatoda*, Traditional Medicine, Phytochemical Screening, Bargarh District.

Introduction:

Justicia adhatoda Linn. belong to the family Acanthaceae. This plant is distributed throughout India, exclusively in the lower Himalayas, Sri Lanka, Burma and Malaysia. It is a dense perennial wild shrub having a height up to 1.2-2.4 m. The stem is aerial, erect, woody, cylindrical, solid, greenish yellow, branched, swollen nodes. Leaves are opposite and decussate, simple, ovate, entire with reticulate venation, 9-8 cm in long; petioles 1-2.5 cm. long. Flowers are bracteate, bracteolate, sessile, complete, hermaphrodite, zygomorphic, pentamerous, hypogynous, whitish with pink streaks. Calyx rather less than 1.3 cm, sepals five in numbers, gamosepalous (Slightly connate at base), imbricate, green in colour. Corolla white, with a few irregular pinkish coloured bars in the throat, five in number,

gamopetalous, bilabiate, imbricate aestivation. Stamens two in number, polyandrous, epipetalous, filament long, hairy at the base, basifixed, dithecous, introse, anther lobes at unequal height and spurred. Gynoecium is bicarpellary, syncarpous, superior, bilocular, one ovule in each locule, axile placentation, style long, stigma bifid. Fruit is capsule type and seeds seated on juncators (Mohanty 2017).

The leaves, roots and young plants of *A. vasica* contain the quinazoline alkaloids vasicine, 7-hydroxyvasicine, vasicinolone, 3- deoxyvasicine, vasicol, vasicoline, vasicolinone, triterpenes, anisotine) betaine, steroids carbohydrate and alkanes. In the flowers triterpenes (a-amirine), and flavonoids (Apigenin, astragalin, kaempferol, quercetin, vitexin) have been found (Kumar *et al.*, 2005). In Ayurveda, the ancient system of Indian medicine it is commonly known as vasaca (Prajapati *et al.*, 2003) which is a well-known plant in indigenous system of medicine. It grows to about a height of 1.5-2.0m with leaves about 10- 15cm long and 5.0cm wide and white or purple flowers and 4-seeded fruits. *Adhatoda* leaves have been used extensively in Ayurvedic Medicine for over 2000 years primarily for respiratory disorders. Roots of the plants is used for the treatment of piles, and leaves are used for the treatment of Leprosy, bronchitis, cough, tuberculosis by the native of Bargarh district, Odisha (Sahu *et al.*, 2010). Similar kinds of reports from Sohela block of Bargarh district, Odisha (Sahu *et al.*, 2013). The leaves of *J. adhatoda* are used for the treatment of bronchitis, cough, and tuberculosis by the native people of Bhawanipatna and it's adjacent areas of Kalahandi District, Odisha (Sahu *et al.*, 2020). Sahu *et al.* (2021) reported that the leaves of the plant are used for the treatment of Leprosy, bronchitis, and cough by *Sahara* tribal groups of Kangaon village of Bargarh district in western Odisha. 5-6 leaves of *J. adhatoda* mixed with 1 gm of seed each of *Dacus carota* and *Raphanus sativus* to control the Menstrual cycle by the native of Bargarh district, Odisha (Sahu & Mishra, 2022). 10-20gm leaf juice taken with 1tsp honey regularly controls asthma. Tea prepared from dry leaves and consumed 3-4 times per day also controls asthma by the Gond tribes of Nabarangpur district, Odisha, India (Sahu & Sahu, 2023). From the leaves of *Adhatoda* yellow colour natural dye was yielding by the native of Jharigaon Block of Nabarangpur district, Odisha (Sahu & Sahu, 2024). Keeping these in mind the present pursuit accentuated upon following objective: To study the ethnobotanical exploration and phytochemical screening of *J. adhatoda* Linn.

Materials and Methods:

Study area

Bargarh is located in the western region of Odisha at an altitude of 171 meters above sea level with a latitude and longitude of 21.342585° North and 83.624199° East, respectively. It consists of 12 blocks under two subdivisions i.e. Bargarh and Padampur. The average temperature during summer season is about 46° C and during winter, it is roughly around 10° C. The land area of Bargarh district is about 5837 square kilometers, of which, about 1216.13 square kilometers (20.83%) is covered in forest area (Sahu *et al.*, 2010; Sahu *et al.*, 2013; Sahu *et al.*, 2016; Sahu *et al.*, 2021; Sahu & Ekka, 2021; Sahu & Sahu, 2021; Sahu & Mishra, 2022). The plants and ethnobotanical data were collected by frequent exploration throughout the area, but before that, a survey was done by taking observations and direct personal interviews of the locals and experts about the use of medicinal plants found in their locality. The information about the ethnomedicinal uses for selected plants were documented and photographs

were taken. The scientific names and family names were further checked by using local flora book (Saxena and Brahman, 1994-1996).

Collection of plant sample

The flowering twigs were collected from Bargarh district, Odisha, India and brought to the Department of Botany, Vikash Degree College, Bargarh for identification. After identification was done by Dr. Alok Ranjan Sahu, Assistant Professor, Department of Botany, Vikash Degree College, Bargarh the leaves were separated for further studies (Fig.1.)

Figure 1: Photograph of *Justicia adhatoda* Linn. having flowers.

Preparation of the extract

The leaves of *Justicia adhatoda* Linn. were washed thoroughly in tap water to remove dust particles. The leaves were then dried in shade at room temperature and made powder by using mechanical grinder. The dried powdered samples were soaked in various ethanol for three to five days and aqueous extract were prepared by soaking the dried powder in distilled water. After five days, the extracts were filtered using No.1 Whatman filter paper and stored in air tight container for further analysis.

Qualitative analysis of phytochemicals

For phytochemical analysis following modified protocols were carried out (Nayak *et al.*, 2024; Sahu *et al.*, 2024; Sharma *et al.*, 2024; Rani *et al.*, 2025).

Test for alkaloids (Mayer's test): 1 ml from both the extract and Mayer's reagent was mixed in a test tube, and observe the colour change. The formation of whitish yellow coloured precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids.

Test for steroids (Liebermann -Burchard test): To 1ml of extract, 2ml of acetic anhydride and 2ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 were added and mixed all the solution gently, and observed the colour change. Formation of violet colour indicates the presence of steroids.

Test for terpenoids (Salkowski test): In a test tube took 1ml of extract and 2ml of chloroform was added in to it, few drops of H_2SO_4 were added and mixed all the solution gently, and observed the colour change. Formation of reddish-brown ring indicates the presence of terpenoids.

Test for flavanoids (Alkaline reagent test): To 1 ml of extract, few drops of dilute ammonium solution and few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid were added. A yellow colouration indicates the presence of flavanoids.

Test for saponins (Froth test): In a test tube took 1ml of extract, 5 ml of distilled water was added and shaken vigorously. Formation of bubbles shows the presence of saponins.

Test for phenols (Lead Acetate test): 1 ml from both the extract and Mayer's reagent was mixed in a test tube, and mixed it gently. Formation of precipitate indicates the presence of phenols.

Test for tannins (Lead acetate test): To 1ml of extract, 1ml of lead acetate was added. A formation of white precipitate indicates the presence of tannins.

Test for tannins (Ferric chloride test): To 1ml of extract, 1ml of ferric chloride solution was added and observe the change in the colour. Formation of blue or brownish green colour show the presence of tannins in the extract.

Test for cardiac glycosides (Keller killiani test): In a test tube took 1ml of extract, 5ml of distilled water was added and evaporated to dryness. Then 2 ml of glacial acetic acid containing trace amount of ferric chloride was added into the test tube. Then 1ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 was added along the sides of the tube. Formation of brown ring under layer with blue colour indicates presence of cardiac glycosides.

Test for amino acids (Ninhydrin test): In a test tube took 1ml of extract, 3 to 4 drops of Ninhydrin solution was added and boiled in water bath for 10 min. Formation of purple colour shows the presence of amino acids in the extract.

Test for proteins (Biuret test): In a test tube took 1ml of extract, 1ml of 40% NaOH solution and 2 drops of 1% copper sulphate solution were added, observed the change in colour. The formation of violet colour shows the presence of proteins.

Test for carbohydrates (Barfoed test): In a test tube took 2ml of extract, 1 ml of Barfoed's reagent was added and boiled in a water bath for few minutes, observed the change in colour. The formation of reddish-brown precipitate indicates the presence of carbohydrates.

Test for reducing sugars (Fehling's test): In a test tube took 1ml of extract, equal quantities of Fehling solution A and B were added and heated, observed the change in colour. The formation of brick red precipitate shows the presence of reducing sugars.

Results:

Traditional utilization

The native of Bargarh district used the leaves of *J. adhatoda* for the treatment of asthma, arthritis, colds, coughs, eczema, malaria, tuberculosis and rheumatism, and as a uterine tonic.

Phytochemical screening

During the phytochemical tests of ethanol extract of *J. adhatoda* leaves, phytochemicals like alkaloids, steroids, terpenoids, saponins, phenols and tannins showed positive result, while flavonoids, cardiac glycosides, amino acids, proteins, carbohydrates and reducing sugar showed negative result. Meanwhile, In the aqueous extracts, alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, saponins, tannins, phenols, amino acids and proteins showed positive result, but steroids, tannins, cardiac glycosides, carbohydrates and reducing sugars showed negative result (Table 1).

Table 1: Phytochemical Screening of *Justicia adhatoda* leaves using Ethanol and Aqueous extracts

Tests	Ethanol	Aqueous
Alkaloids	+	+
Steroids	+	-
Flavonoids	-	+
Terpenoids	+	+
Saponins	+	+
Phenols	+	+
Tannins	+	-
Cardiac Glycosides	-	-
Amino acids	-	+
Proteins	-	+
Carbohydrates	-	-
Reducing Sugars	-	-
Abbreviation: + (Present), - (Absent)		

Discussion:

Traditional medicine has utilized *J. adhatoda* for centuries to treat various ailments. In Ayurveda, it has tikta, kashaya, laghu, sheeta, and virya properties. Thus, it may help for the treatment of the heart and respiratory diseases. It was initially used to treat respiratory diseases, but its use has grown steadily over time (Kumar *et al.*, 2010). Leaves are used traditionally for the betterment of cough, asthma, hepato-protective, bronchitis, tuberculosis, and as a uterine tonic (Bhattacharyya *et al.*, 2005). The fluid extract was used in Europe to treat spasms, typhus fever, coughs, and as a febrifuge (Amin *et al.*, 2013). It was an expectorant and antispasmodic in Germany. Sweden people used to treat cough. The whole plant is used in Sri Lanka for phlegm, menorrhagia, and piles. The leaves are smoked to cure asthma (Hossain & Hoq, 2016). The ethanolic extract of leaves were used to conquer infective organisms (Karthikeyan *et al.*, 2009). It is commonly utilized in South East Asian indigenous and folk medicine (Singh *et al.*, 2011). The Naga tribes utilize a leaf concoction to treat intestinal worms and also as an anti-bacterial agent (Yadav & Tangpu, 2008; Mehreen *et al.*, 2016). Our findings suggest that *J. adhatoda* is a wonder plant, as it is utilized to heal various ailments. The scientist discovered that the traditional assertion that *J. adhatoda* can be used to cure different conditions is true, especially in the case of respiratory diseases. Roots of the plants is used for the treatment of piles, and leaves are used

for the treatment of Leprosy, bronchitis, cough, tuberculosis by the native of Bargarh district, Odisha (Sahu *et al.*, 2010). Similar kinds of reports from Sohela block of Bargarh district, Odisha (Sahu *et al.*, 2013). The leaves of *J. adhatoda* are used for the treatment of bronchitis, cough, and tuberculosis by the native people of Bhawanipatna and its adjacent areas of Kalahandi District, Odisha (Sahu *et al.*, 2020). Sahu *et al.* (2021) reported that the leaves of the plant are used for the treatment of Leprosy, bronchitis, and cough by Sahara tribal groups of Kangaon village of Bargarh district in western Odisha. 5-6 leaves of *J. adhatoda* mixed with 1 gm of seed each of *Dacus carota* and *Raphanus sativus* to control the Menstrual cycle by the native of Bargarh district, Odisha (Sahu & Mishra, 2022). 10-20gm leaf juice taken with 1tsp honey regularly controls asthma. Tea prepared from dry leaves and consumed 3-4 times per day also controls asthma by the Gond tribes of Nabarangpur district, Odisha, India (Sahu & Sahu, 2023). From the leaves of *Adhatoda* yellow colour natural dye was yielding by the native of Jharigaon Block of Nabarangpur district, Odisha (Sahu & Sahu, 2024).

The present study on phytochemical screening of *J. adhatoda* plant showed following results. During the respective phytochemical tests of ethanol extract of *J. adhatoda* leaves, phytochemicals like alkaloids, steroids, terpenoids, saponins, phenols and tannins showed positive result, while flavonoids, cardiac glycosides, amino acids, proteins, carbohydrates and reducing sugar showed negative result. Meanwhile, In the aqueous extracts, alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, saponins, tannins, phenols, amino acids and proteins showed positive result, but steroids, tannins, cardiac glycosides, carbohydrates and reducing sugars showed negative result. Malathi *et al.* (2019) studied on phytochemical analysis of *J. adhatoda* leaves and revealed that the phytochemicals present in the extract of *J. adhatoda* are alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, cardiac glycosides, coumarins, hydroxy anthraquinones, tannins, phlobatannins, proteins, xantho protein, steroids and phenols. The diversity of phytochemical present in the plant suggests that this plant might help as a basis of several helpful drugs. Reddy *et al.* (2015) evaluated the physico-chemical, and preliminary phytochemical of different extracts on the flowers of *J. adhatoda* L. Preliminary phytochemical screening of the extracts showed the presence of alkaloids, carbohydrates, flavonoides, phenols, proteins, saponins and tannins.

Conclusion:

The native of Bargarh district used the leaves of *Justicia adhatoda* L. for the treatment of asthma, arthritis, colds, coughs, eczema, malaria, tuberculosis and rheumatism, and as a uterine tonic. From the phytochemical screening it has been shown that alkaloids, terpenoids, saponins, phenols were present in both ethanol and aqueous extracts. Both the steroids and tannins are present in only ethanol extract, while amino acids and proteins are present only in aqueous extract. While carbohydrates and reducing sugars showed negative results for both the aqueous and ethanol extracts.

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References:

1. Amin, M., Anwar, F., Naz, F., Mehmood, T., & Saari, N. (2013). Anti-Helicobacter pylori and urease inhibition activities of some traditional medicinal plants. *Molecules*, 18(2), 2135-2149.

2. Bhattacharyya, D., Pandit, S., Jana, U., Sen, S., & Sur, T. K. (2005). Hepatoprotective activity of *Adhatoda vasica* aqueous leaf extract on D-galactosamine-induced liver damage in rats. *Fitoterapia*, 76(2), 223-225.
3. Hossain, M. T., & Hoq, M. O. (2016). Therapeutic use of *Adhatoda vasica*. *Asian Journal of Medical and Biological Research*, 2(2), 156-163.
4. Kumar, A., Ram, J., Samarth, R. M., & Kumar, M. (2005). Modulatory influence of *Adhatoda vasica* Nees leaf extract against gamma irradiation in Swiss albino mice. *Phytomedicine*, 12, 285-293.
5. Kumar, K. S., Debjit, B., Pankaj, T., & Rakesh, K. (2010). Indian traditional herbs *Adhatoda vasica* and its medicinal application. *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, 2(1), 240-245.
6. Malathi, R., Kaviyaran, D., & Chandrasekar, S. (2019). Study on Preliminary Photochemical and GC-MS Analysis of *Justicia adhatoda* Leaves Extract. *Journal of Drug Delivery & Therapeutics*, 9(4-s), 547-550
7. Mehreen, A., Waheed, M., Liaqat, I., & Arshad, N. (2016). Phytochemical, Antimicrobial, and Toxicological Evaluation of Traditional Herbs Used to Treat Sore Throat. *BioMed research international*, 2016, 8503426. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/8503426>.
8. Mohanty, C. R. (2018). Textbook of Plant Systematics, Kalyani Publisher, New Delhi.
9. Prajapati, N., Purohit, S., Sharma, D., & Tarun, K. (2003). A Handbook of Medicinal Plants. 1st Edn, agrobios. Jodhpur, India. P.p. 13-14.
10. Reddy, M. P., Shantha, T. R., Rao, V. R., & Venkateswarlu, G. (2015). Pharmacognostical and Physicochemical Evaluation on the Flowers of *Justicia adhatoda* L. *Research Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 7(2): 73-90
11. Sahu AR, Behera N and Mishra SP (2010). Use of Ethnomedicinal Plants by Natives of Bargarh District of Orissa, India. *Ethnobotanical Leaflets* 14: 889-910.
12. Sahu AR, Ekka NJ (2021). A preliminary report on the use of leafy vegetables by the native of Bargarh district, Western Odisha, India. *International Journal of Applied Research* 7(5): 218-223. (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22271/allresearch.2021.v7.i5d.8567>).
13. Sahu AR, Mishra S (2022). Plants used for the treatment of Gynecological disorders by the native of Bargarh district, Western Odisha, India. In *Recent Trends and Advances in Medicinal Plants Research*, Soni PK (eds.) PK Publishers and Distributors, 4th Pustak Kartar Nagar, New Delhi, Chapter 6, Pp. 71- 76. (ISBN: 978-81-953735-8-1).
14. Sahu AR, Nayak AK, Panigrahi SK (2013). Survey of some important ethno-medicinal plants of Sohela Block, Western Odisha, India. *Life Sciences Leaflets* 11(11): 1-9.
15. Sahu AR, Sahu M (2021). A preliminary report on the ethnobotanical plants used for dental care by the tribal of Bargarh District, Western Odisha. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences* 9 (2): 1020-1028.
16. Sahu AR, Sahu M, Mishra S, Ekka NJ (2021). A preliminary Report on Ethnomedicinal uses of Selected Plants by *Sahara* Tribal Groups of Kangaon Village of Bargarh District in Western

- Odisha. Journal of Medicinal Plants Studies 9(3): 238-242. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22271/plants.2021.v9.i3c.1300>.
17. Sahu AR, Sahu M, Nayak NR and Sahoo TR (2020). Medicinal Plants of Saraswati +3 Science College, Bhawanipatna Campus and it's adjacent areas, Kalahandi district, South-Western Odisha, India. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences 9 (1): 1738-1752 (DOI: 10.20959/wjpps20201-15408).
 18. Sahu M, and Sahu AR (2024) A Report on Ethno-Colour Concept among the Gond Tribal peoples of Jharigaon block, Nabarangpur District, Odisha, India. In From Cells to Ecosystems: Exploring Life Science Research; Kadam SS, Sahu AR, Sarvajana S, and Verma S (Ed.). Bhumi Publishing, Nigave Khalasa, Kolhapur 416207, Maharashtra, INDIA. (ISBN: 978-93-95847-22-3), Volume II, Pp. 108-116.
 19. Sahu, A. R., & Sahu, M. (2023). A preliminary Report on Ethnomedicinal Study of Plants Used to Treat Asthma by the Gond Tribes of Nabarangpur District, Odisha, India. In **Frontiers in Life Science Volume X**; Parimala, B., Mishra, P., Yadav, K. K., & Sahu, A. R. (Ed.). Bhumi Publishing, Nigave Khalasa, Kolhapur 416207, Maharashtra, India. Chapter 1, Pp. 1- 10. (ISBN: **978-93-88901-35-2**).
 20. Singh, T. P., Singh O. M., & Singh H. B. (2011). *Adhatoda vasica* Nees: phytochemical and pharmacological profile. The Natural Products Journal, 1(1), 29-39.
 21. Yadav, A. K., & Tangpu, V. (2008). Anticestodal activity of *Adhatoda vasica* extract against *Hymenolepis diminuta* infections in rats. *J Ethnopharmacol*, 119(2), 322-324.